

Phase-II metabolism limits the antiproliferative activity of urolithins in human colon cancer cells

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ABSTRACT

Purpose Urolithins, gut microbiota metabolites derived from ellagic acid and ellagitannins, reach micromolar concentrations in the colon lumen where can have anti-inflammatory and anticancer effects. The antiproliferative activity of urolithins (Uro-A, -B, -C, -D) and their most relevant *in vivo* glucuronides were evaluated in three human colon cancer cell lines (Caco-2, SW480 and HT-29).

Methods Cell proliferation was evaluated by MTT and Trypan blue exclusion assays. Cell cycle was evaluated by flow cytometry and urolithins metabolism by HPLC-MS/MS.

Results Urolithins inhibited cell proliferation and cell cycle progression in a time- and dose- dependent manner and arrested the cells at S and G2/M phases, depending on the urolithin. Uro-A exerted the highest antiproliferative activity, followed by Uro-C, -D and -B. Unlike Caco-2 and SW480 cells, HT-29 cells partially overcame the effects after 48 h, which was related to the complete glucuronidation of urolithins. Uro-A or -B glucuronides did not affect cell cycle and showed lower antiproliferative activity than their aglycone counterparts. Uro-A or Uro-B plus inhibitors of drug efflux ABC transporters partially prevented the glucuronidation of urolithins in HT-29 cells which became more sensitive.

Conclusions Uro-A, -B, -C and -D exerted different antiproliferative effects depending on the colon cancer cell line. We also report here, for the first time, the role of ABC transporters and Phase-II metabolism in HT-29 cells as a mechanism of cancer resistance against urolithins due to their conversion to glucuronide conjugates that exerted lower antiproliferative activity.

KEYWORDS: urolithins; ellagic acid; glucuronide; cell cycle; colon cancer; phase-II metabolism.

INTRODUCTION

Colorectal cancer remains as one of the major causes of cancer-related mortality in both genders, with prevalence mainly in Western countries and their incidence continues to rise every year [1]. Numerous animal and cell culture studies have indicated a potential cancer chemopreventive role of polyphenols, and polyphenols-containing commodities. Thus, a wide range of mechanisms which lead to inhibition of the carcinogenesis process such as proliferation inhibition, cell-cycle arrest and/or the induction of apoptosis on cancer cells have been reported [2-4].

Ellagitannins are polyphenols present in a wide range of foodstuffs such as pomegranates, strawberries, raspberries, walnuts, and oak-aged wines [5]. Ellagitannins are hydrolyzable tannins releasing ellagic acid on hydrolysis which is further metabolized by the gut microbiota to form urolithins [6, 7]. These metabolites, mainly urolithin A and B (Uro-A and Uro-B), have been identified in animals [8-10], as well as in humans [11, 12], indicating that they can reach systemic organs such as the prostate. It should be noted that after the intake of ellagitannins-containing foods, the main metabolites detected in the plasma of humans, at low μM concentrations, were the glucuronides of Uro-A and Uro-B [13], whereas the highest concentrations of urolithin aglycones, mainly Uro-A (up to 100 μM), have been reported in the colon [8, 9].

In the past few years, a number of *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies have shown a wide range of biological activities for urolithins, mainly Uro-A, such as anticancer [9, 14-17], anti-inflammatory [18-21], antimalarial [22], anti-bacterial [23], and estrogenic/anti-estrogenic [24]. All these studies indicated that Uro-A showed the highest biological activity.

Recently, the main *in vivo* conjugates, Uro-A and Uro-B glucuronides have been reported to exert lower effect than their aglycone counterparts in the reduction of TNF- α -induced inflammation mediated by inhibition of monocyte adhesion and endothelial cell migration, and decreased

associated molecular markers in human aortic endothelial cells [25]. However, the anticancer activity of urolithin glucuronides has not yet been evaluated. This is important since Uro-A, the most relevant urolithin, has been reported to be substrate for the drug efflux protein ABCG2/BCRP [26] and these ABC transporters are involved in Phase-II metabolism of xenobiotics and mechanisms of cancer resistance [27]. In this context, our aim was to compare the effects of urolithins (Uro-A, -B, -C, -D) and their most relevant *in vivo* glucuronides (Uro-A and Uro-B glucuronides; Fig. 1) on cell proliferation and cell cycle distribution in three human colon cancer cell lines (Caco-2, SW480 and HT-29) and to evaluate whether glucuronidation of urolithins could be a possible mechanism of resistance in these cancer cells.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials and reagents

Urolithin A (3,8-dihydroxy-6H-dibenzo[*b,d*]pyran-6-one; Uro-A), urolithin B (3-hydroxy-6H-dibenzo[*b,d*]pyran-6-one; Uro-B) and urolithin B glucuronide were synthesized by Villapharma Research (Fuente Álamo, Murcia, Spain). Urolithin A glucuronide (Uro-A glur) was prepared according to Giménez-Bastida [25]. Urolithin C (3,7,8-trihydroxy-6H-dibenzo[*b,d*]pyran-6-one, Uro-C) and urolithin D (2,3,7,8-tetrahydroxy-6H-dibenzo[*b,d*]pyran-6-one, Uro-D) were purchased from Dalton Pharma Services (Toronto, Canada). Purity was higher than 95% in all tested compounds. Trypan blue, 3-(4,5-Dimethyl-2-thiazolyl)-2,5-diphenyl-2H-tetrazolium bromide (MTT), Ko143, CP100356 and probenecid were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, USA). Phosphate Buffered Saline (PBS) was from Fisher Scientific (USA). DMSO, diethyl-ether and HPLC reagents, formic acid and ACN, were obtained from Panreac (Barcelona, Spain). Methanol (MeOH) was from Lab-Scan (Gliwice, Poland). Ultrapure Millipore water was used for all solutions.

Cell lines and culture conditions

Cell lines were obtained from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC, Rockville, USA) and cultured as recommended by the ATCC. Human colon cancer cell line Caco-2 were grown in minimal essential medium (MEM) supplemented with 10% v/v fetal bovine serum (FBS), 1% v/v non-essential amino acids, 1% v/v L-glutamine, 100 U/mL penicillin and 100 µg/mL streptomycin (Gibco, Invitrogen S.A., Barcelona, Spain). The human colon cancer cells HT-29 were grown in Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (DMEM; 4.5 g/L D-glucose) containing 10% v/v fetal bovine serum, 1% v/v nonessential amino acids, 1% v/v L-glutamine, and 1% v/v antibiotic solution. Finally, the colon cancer cells SW480 were grown in Leibovitz's L-15 medium supplemented with 10% v/v fetal bovine serum, 1% v/v L-glutamine, and 1% v/v antibiotic solution. Cells were maintained at 37 °C in an incubator under a 5% CO₂/95% air atmosphere at constant humidity, except SW480 cells that were incubated without CO₂. Cells were counted using a hemacytometer and were plated at 15,000 (Caco-2 and HT-29) and 30,000 (SW480) cells cm⁻² for 48 h prior to pure compounds addition. All of the test samples were solubilized in DMSO (<0.5% in the culture medium) and were filter sterilised (0.2 µm) prior to addition to the culture media. Control cells were also run in parallel and subjected to the same changes in medium with a 0.5% DMSO. In addition, cells were treated for 24, 48, 72 and/or 96 h, depending of experiment, at 100 and 50 µM of Uro-A and -B aglycones and glucuronides.

Cell proliferation and viability tests

After 24 and 48 h of each treatment, trypsinized cells (2.5 g/L trypsin, 0.2 g/L EDTA) were suspended in cell culture medium, counted using a Neubauer haemocytometer (Bad Mergentheim, Germany) and viability and proliferation measured using Trypan blue dye exclusion. Viability and

proliferation results in treated cells are expressed as percentage of those values obtained for control (0.5% DMSO) cells. All experiments were performed in triplicate.

To confirm these data, cell proliferation was also evaluated by measuring the reduction of soluble MTT [3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide] to water insoluble formazan [28]. All observations were validated by at least three independent experiments and for each experiment.

Analysis of cell cycle by flow cytometry

Cells (2×10^5) were collected after the corresponding experimental periods, fixed in ice-cold ethanol: PBS (70:30) for 30 min at 4 °C, further resuspended in PBS with 100 µg/mL RNase and 40 µg/mL propidium iodide, and incubated at 37 °C for 30 min. DNA content (25,000 cells) was analysed using a FACScan instrument equipped with FACStation running Cell Quest software (Becton Dickinson, New Jersey, USA). The analyses of cell cycle distribution were performed in triplicate for each treatment. The coefficient of variation, according to the ModFit LT Version 2 acquisition software package (Verity Software House, Topsham, ME, USA), was always less than 5%. The analyses of cell cycle distribution were performed in triplicate ($n = 2$ plates per experiment) for each treatment (100 and 50 µM) for time points at 24 and 48 h.

Determination of metabolites in cell media

Culture media were processed as described by Giménez-Bastida [25]. Briefly, cell culture supernatants were collected at the end of the experiment and analyzed to measure the presence and concentration of the tested compounds. ACN (250 µL) was added per 100 µL of culture media, vortexed and centrifuged at $16435 \times g$ for 10 min. The supernatant was then concentrated in a

Speedvac® concentrator (Savant SPD 121P) and the residue re-dissolved in 100 µL of MeOH, diluted in water (1:1) and filtered (0.45 µm) before analysis by HPLC-MS/MS.

Processed cell media were analyzed using an Agilent 1100 HPLC system equipped with a photodiode-array detector and an ion-trap mass spectrometer detector in series (Agilent Technologies, Waldbronn, Germany). Chromatographic separation was carried out on a reverse phase LiChroCART C-18 column (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) (250 x 4 mm, 4.5 µm particle size) using water with 1% formic acid (A) and acetonitrile (B) as the mobile phases. The gradient profile was: 0-20 min, 5-30% B, 20-30 min, 30-55% B, 30-38 min, 55-90% B, this percentage was maintained for 2 minutes and then came back to the initial conditions. A volume of 10 µL of sample was injected onto the column operating at room temperature and a flow rate of 1 mL/min. The HPLC system was coupled in series to an ion trap mass spectrometer (IT) equipped with an electrospray interface (ESI). Nitrogen was used as drying gas with flow of 11 L/min and temperature of 350 °C and nebulizing gas at pressure of 65 psi. The capillary voltage was set at 4 kV. Mass scan (MS) and daughter (MS-MS) spectra were recorded in negative mode in the range of m/z 100-700 with target mass of 300. Maximum accumulation time of ion trap and the number of MS repetitions to obtain the MS average spectra were set at 200 ms and 3, respectively. Compound stability was set at 75 %. Identification of all tested compounds was carried out by direct comparison (UV spectra and MS) with available standards and confirmed by their spectral properties, molecular mass and fragmentation pattern. Urolithin aglycones and glucuronides were confirmed by their spectral properties, molecular mass and fragmentation pattern. Calibration curves were obtained for each tested compounds with good linearity ($r^2 > 0.999$). Quantification of all urolithins and their conjugates was made at 305 nm using the corresponding available standards.

Statistical analysis

All data are presented as mean values \pm SD. Two-tailed unpaired Student's t-test was used for statistical analysis of the data. A p value < 0.05 was considered significant.

RESULTS

Effect of urolithin aglycones on cell viability

Compounds were not cytotoxic at the tested doses (100 and 50 μ M) since cell viability was always above 90% and was constant throughout the experimental period and similar to that of control cells (data not shown).

Antiproliferative activity of urolithin aglycones

Cell proliferation of colon cancer cell lines was evaluated using both Trypan blue and MTT methods after treatments with urolithins (Uro-A, -B, -C, and -D) (100 and 50 μ M) and compared to control cells (0.5% DMSO). Preliminary experiments using concentrations below 50 μ M showed no significant effects on cell proliferation assays. Therefore, higher concentrations, but still physiologically relevant in the colon lumen, were selected in order to get significant effects.

The effect of urolithins on cell proliferation is shown in Fig. 2. Caco-2 cells were the most sensitive cells to urolithin treatments, followed by SW480 and HT-29. The proliferation of Caco-2 cells was significantly inhibited ($p < 0.05$) in a concentration- and time-dependent manner by all urolithins, reaching cell proliferation values less than 30% at 48 h for Uro-A, -C and -D (100 μ M), and around 50% for Uro-B at 48 h (100 μ M) (Fig. 2A). The proliferation of SW480 cells was significantly inhibited ($p < 0.05$) by Uro-A, -C, and -D, showing cell proliferation values around 30- 40% at 48 h (100 μ M) in a dose- and time-dependent manner, except for Uro-D at 50 μ M where

inhibition was not time-dependent. The treatment with Uro-B showed a slight, although significant ($p < 0.05$) proliferation inhibition at 100 μM , whereas no inhibition was observed at 50 μM (Fig. 2B). Finally, the incubation of HT-29 cells with urolithins showed that Uro-A and -C exerted higher proliferation inhibition than Uro-B and -D, with inhibition values around 40% and 70% ($p < 0.05$) at 48 h (100 μM), respectively (Fig. 2C). It should be noted that the antiproliferative activity exerted by urolithins in HT-29 cells was less effective, especially at 50 μM , when compared with the other two cell lines (Fig. 2). Moreover, in contrast to the other cell lines, antiproliferative effects of urolithins were attenuated in this cell line after 48 h (Fig. 2).

Effect of urolithin aglycones on cell cycle distribution

The highest effects on cell cycle distribution were observed in Caco-2 cells, which was in agreement with antiproliferative effects observed. Uro-A exerted a significant arrest at G₂/M and S phases ($p < 0.05$) at 24 h, whereas Uro-B, -C and -D showed significant arrest at S phase ($p < 0.05$). These arrests were increased at 48 h, and were accompanied by a significant decrease of cells in G₀/G₁ phase at both incubation times (Fig. 3A). Regarding SW480 cells, treatments with Uro-A induced arrest at G₂/M and S phases ($p < 0.05$), whereas Uro-D and -C arrested at S phase after 24 h ($p < 0.05$). Similar to Caco-2 cells, these arrests were maintained at 48 h. In agreement to the inhibition of cell proliferation, Uro-B did not show significant effects on the cell cycle of SW480 cells (Fig. 3B).

In the case of HT-29 cells, Uro-A induced arrest at G₂/M and S phases ($p < 0.05$), whereas Uro-B (100 μM) and Uro-C and -D exerted a significant arrest ($p < 0.05$) at S phase after 24 h (Fig. 3C). In contrast to the other cell lines, no cell cycle alteration was observed at 48 h, except for Uro-A that arrested the cells at G₂/M although the effects were lower than those observed at 24 h ($p < 0.05$). In

addition, Uro-C and -D induced significant arrest at S phase only at 100 μM ($p < 0.05$) and showed also lower effects after 48 h than those obtained at 24 h (Fig. 3C).

Overall, these results showed a dose- and time-dependent cell cycle alteration in both Caco-2 and SW480 cells, but not in HT-29 cells. Therefore, HT-29 cells showed a higher resistance over time when compared with Caco-2 and SW480 cells which became more evident with the lowest concentration (50 μM). We next investigated the cell metabolism of urolithins in these three cell lines in order to provide further insight into the possible mechanisms of resistance in HT-29 cells to face urolithins treatments.

Cell metabolism of urolithin aglycones

After incubation of Caco-2 and SW480 cells with both Uro-A and -B, the HPLC-MS/MS analysis of cell media showed a decrease in the concentration of both urolithins, despite urolithins conjugated were hardly detected (only a small amount of Uro-A glucuronide in Caco-2 cells after 48 h; results not shown). This suggested a slow metabolism of urolithins by Caco-2 cells and an apparent lack of metabolism in SW480 cells. On the contrary, HT-29 cells were able to glucuronidate urolithins, detecting only a small amount of remaining urolithin aglycones at 24 h while the transformation to glucuronides was complete after 48 h (Fig. 4).

In the case of Uro-C, no conjugated metabolites were detected in SW480 cells, whereas a low amount of glucuronide conjugates were found in Caco-2 cells (data not shown). However, in the case of HT-29 cells, three glucuronide conjugates, as well as other three methyl-glucuronide from Uro-C were detected (Fig. 4). In addition, shorter incubation times (2, 4, 8, 12 and 24 h) demonstrated that HT-29 cells started with the production of glucuronides followed by their methylation (data not shown).

Unfortunately, in the case of Uro-D neither the aglycone nor its conjugated metabolites could be identified at the same incubation times and following the same protocols (data not shown). The use of different extraction protocols did not succeed in the recovery of Uro-D from the cell media. Further experiments revealed the instability of Uro-D in the cell media due to temperature (37 °C) and pH (7.3) (data not shown).

Effect of urolithin glucuronides on cell proliferation and cell cycle distribution

We next evaluated the effect of Uro-A and Uro-B glucuronides (using the available standards) on the proliferation of HT-29 cells in order to ascertain whether the conversion of aglycones to glucuronides in this cell line was critical as a mechanism of resistance. Table 1 shows the comparison of cell proliferation inhibition data between Uro-A and -B aglycones and their corresponding glucuronides in the three cancer cell lines.

Both Uro-A and -B glucuronides (100 µM) inhibited Caco-2 cells proliferation by 30 and 20%, respectively, at 48 h. Regarding SW480 cells, Uro-A glucuronide (100 µM) inhibited by 25% cell proliferation at 48 h ($p < 0.05$), whereas Uro-B glucuronide did not exert significant inhibition on cell proliferation (Table 1). In the case of HT-29 cells, proliferation was slightly, but significantly ($p < 0.05$) inhibited by Uro-A and Uro-B glucuronides (10%) at 48 h. In all cases, inhibition values were remarkably lower than those obtained after treatments with urolithin aglycones (Table 1).

In addition, treatments with either Uro-A glucuronide or Uro-B glucuronide did not exert significant effects on cell cycle distribution in any cell line after 24 or 48 h (results not shown).

Activity of urolithin-A or -B in the presence of ABC transporter inhibitors in HT-29 cells

We next tried to confirm the possible role of ABC transporters in the mechanism of resistance

of HT-29 cells against urolithins. HT-29 cells were treated with urolithins in the presence of different ABC transporter inhibitors to hamper the transport of urolithins into the cells and their further metabolism to glucuronides. Uro-A and Uro-B were selected because their corresponding glucuronides were available, and also because the glucuronidation of Uro-A and -B was almost complete in HT-29 cells after 24 h of treatment (Fig. 4).

ABC transporter inhibitors were used at non-toxic concentrations and were added to cells 1 h before the treatments with urolithins -A and -B for 24 and 48 h. First, we evaluated the metabolism of urolithins with or without three ABC transporter inhibitors. The P-gp inhibitor CP100356 (1 μ M) caused the highest reduction in the conversion of Uro-A and Uro-B into their corresponding glucuronides, although around 50% and 60% of Uro-A and -B, respectively, were conjugated to their corresponding glucuronides at 24 h, reaching values around 80% and 90% of Uro-A and -B, respectively, at 48 h (Fig. 5A). In contrast, Ko143 (1 μ M), a potent and selective BCRP inhibitor, moderately prevented the glucuronidation in HT-29 cells after co-incubation with Uro-B or Uro-A (~70% and ~80% of conversion, respectively) at 24 h. The co-incubation with Probenecid, a MRP inhibitor, showed similar results to Ko143, although in this case it was more effective for Uro-A (~65% of conversion) than for Uro-B (~85% of conversion) at 24 h. Glucuronidation of Uro-B was complete in the presence of Ko143 or Probenecid after 48 h, whereas glucuronidation of Uro-A was more than 90% and 95% in the presence of Probenecid or Ko143, respectively (Fig. 5A).

In comparison to the corresponding urolithin treatments alone, the highest HT-29 cell proliferation inhibition was detected after co-incubating either Uro-A or Uro-B plus CP100356 (Fig. 5B). However, despite using a non-cytotoxic concentration, CP100356 alone (in the absence of Uro-A or Uro-B) exerted a significant arrest at G₀/G₁ phase (data not shown) with a concomitant reduction of cell proliferation by 20%. Therefore, this indicated that the incubation of Uro-A with

either CP100356 or Probenecid yielded similar results in the inhibition of cell proliferation (Fig. 5B) as Probenecid alone did not exert antiproliferative effects (results not shown). However, the treatment of CP100356 plus Uro-B was more effective than Probenecid plus Uro-B in the inhibition of cell proliferation (Fig. 5B). The treatment of Ko143 plus Uro-B also inhibited cell proliferation significantly, whereas no significant differences were found for Ko143 plus Uro-A at 24 h and probenecid plus Uro-B at 24 and 48 h, which matched with the effects on the glucuronidation rate of both urolithins (Fig. 5).

Cell cycle distribution matched with cell proliferation data indicating a higher arrest at S and G₂/M phases after co-incubation with CP100356 in both urolithins compared to the corresponding treatments without inhibitor (results not shown). Co-incubations with Probenecid plus Uro-A, as well as Ko143 plus Uro-B also showed significant arrest at S and G₂/M phases, but lower than those obtained in the presence of CP100356 (data not shown).

DISCUSSION

Molecules with reactive moieties such as hydroxyl groups (-OH) present in phenolic and related compounds are substrates for Phase-II enzymes (i.e., catechol-*O*-methyl transferase, glucuronyl transferases, sulfate transferases, etc.). The resulting conjugated metabolites (glucuronides, sulfates, sulfoglucuronides, methyl-glucuronides, etc.) are less reactive, more hydrophilic and can be better eliminated [29]. The conjugated metabolites of phenolic compounds can maintain certain biological activity but it is usually much lower than that exerted by their aglycone counterparts as previously reported for quercetin [30], resveratrol [31] and others.

Phase-II metabolism can limit the bioavailability of phenolic compounds and related compounds and it is known that the detoxifying action of Phase-II metabolism can be used as a mechanism of cancer resistance by different type of tumor cells [32]. In this context, the ATP-binding cassette

(ABC) transporters play an important role. ABC transporters can affect the pharmacokinetics and disposition of drugs and other compounds in tissues, and mediate drug-drug interactions [27, 33]. In addition, the modulation of ABC transporters can affect chemotherapeutic treatments by modulating the pharmacokinetic behavior of anticancer drugs [34, 35]. Recently, Uro-A, the most relevant urolithin produced by the human gut microbiota was reported to be substrate for the drug efflux transport protein ABCG2/BCRP [26].

Preclinical studies have reported a number of health-beneficial effects for urolithins [36]. These metabolites, mainly Uro-A, can be found at high micromolar concentration in the colon lumen whereas their metabolites, mainly glucuronides, can be detected at nanomolar or low micromolar concentration in the blood stream and systemic organs such as the human prostate [8, 10-12].

A few studies have reported the effect of urolithins on different cancer cell lines. In the present study, we report for the first time a comparative study dealing with the effects of urolithins on three colon cancer cells. In addition, the antiproliferative activity of the most relevant urolithin glucuronides is also reported here for the first time. Our data revealed that urolithins exerted different antiproliferative effects depending on the cell line, in agreement with previous reports [15, 17, 24, 37]. Caco-2 was the most sensitive cell line to urolithins treatments followed by SW480 and HT-29.

Early studies reported the lack of effect on the inhibition of cell proliferation, apoptosis and cell cycle distribution in MCF-7 cells after treatment with either Uro-A or Uro-B (40 μ M) [24]. In the present study, the highest activity was observed for Uro-A and Uro-C followed by Uro-D and Uro- B, respectively. Cell proliferation was inhibited by Uro-A in the three lines mediated by cell cycle arrest at S and G₂/M phases, whereas the rest of urolithins exerted antiproliferative activity mediated by cell cycle arrest at S phase. These results were in agreement with a previous study where the

antiproliferative activity of Uro-A (40 μ M) was higher than that of Uro-B (40 μ M) in Caco-2 colon cancer cells [15]. In addition, a time-dependent arrest of Caco-2 cells at G₂/M and S phases for Uro-A and Uro-B, respectively, was observed [15]. Our results also agree with those reported by Kasimsetty [17] who found arrest of HT-29 cells at G₂/M and S phases by Uro-A and at G₂/M phase by Uro-B after 48 h of treatment.

Urolithins exerted time-dependent effects on Caco-2 and SW480 cells, but not on HT-29 cells as lower antiproliferative and cell cycle effects were observed at 48 h vs 24 h. This became more evident with treatments at 50 μ M. The explanation for this, at least partially, was based on the high glucuronidation rate of urolithins in HT-29 cells, much higher than that in Caco-2 and SW480 cells. The correlation between the effects observed and the presence of metabolites in the cell media is not always evident. This was the case for Uro-D, which showed a marked instability in the cell media even at short incubation times. However, its effects on cell proliferation and cell cycle were evident. The instability of Uro-D could be explained by the presence of *o*-diphenolic moieties in its molecular structure. In this regard, similar behavior has been reported for other phenolics and related metabolites which also showed high instability in cell cultures but evident effects such as the case of piceatannol [38], punicalagin [39] and others. Further research is needed to ascertain whether the metabolite triggers significant effects on the cells before its evolution to other compounds and/or these new compounds are also active.

Previous studies have reported the overexpression of UDP-glucuronosyltransferase enzymes (UGTs), mainly UGT1A1 in HT-29 cells [40, 41]. On the contrary, other studies described a low expression and activity of UGTs in Caco-2 and SW480 cells [42, 43]. Therefore, the differential expression of UGTs could explain the different glucuronidation capacity of these cell lines. In

addition, a previous study in Caco-2 cells showed that incubation with UroA and UroB (40 μ M) slightly induced the RNA expression of UGT1A10 [9].

The role of ABC transporters in the transport of phenolic compounds and their conjugates is well known [44]. Our results, using selective ABC transporter inhibitors, suggest indirectly that the ABC transporters P-gp and MRP could play an important role in the transport and detoxifying processes of urolithins in HT-29 cells. Uro-A and its sulfate conjugate, but not other urolithins or derived conjugated, were previously described as ABCG2/BCRP substrates in human, murine, ovine and bovine BCRP-transduced subclones of MDCKII cells (Mardin-Darby canine kidney) [26]. However, the use of the BCRP inhibitor Ko143 in HT-29 cells seemed to affect more significantly Uro-B metabolism than that of Uro-A.

Overall, our results suggest that urolithins A, B, C and D exerted different effects on cell proliferation and cycle distribution depending on the colon cancer cell line. Unlike Caco-2 and SW480 cells, HT-29 cells were able to partially overcome the antiproliferative activity of urolithins by forming the corresponding glucuronide conjugates. In this mechanism of cancer resistance, ABC transporters and Phase-II metabolism seem to play a critical role. We also report here for the first time that Uro-A glucuronide and Uro-B glucuronide exert antiproliferative activity, although this activity is lower than that of their aglycone counterparts using these colon cancer cell lines. In this regard, our results warrant further investigations using cells from systemic organs where urolithin glucuronides, but not the aglycones, are the most relevant metabolites detected.

ABBREVIATIONS USED

ABC, ATP-binding cassette; ACN, acetonitrile; ATP, Adenosine-5'-triphosphate; BCRP, breast cancer resistance protein; DMEM, Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium; DMSO, dimethyl sulfoxide; DNA, deoxyribonucleic acid; EDTA, ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid; ESI, electrospray interface; Gluc, glucuronide; HPLC; High-performance liquid chromatography; IT, ion trap; MDCKII, Mardin-Darby canine kidney; MEM, minimal essential medium; MeOH, methanol; MRP, Multidrug Resistant Protein; MS, mass spectrometry; MTT, 3-(4,5-Dimethyl-2-thiazolyl)-2,5-diphenyl-2H-tetrazolium bromide; OH-, hydroxyl groups; PBS, phosphate buffered saline; P-gp, P-glycoprotein; RNA, ribonucleic acid; SD, standard deviation; TNF- α , tumor necrosis factor alpha; UGTs, UDP-glucuronosyltransferases; Uro, Urolithins; UV, ultraviolet; μ M, micromolar.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

Authors declare no conflict of interests

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Figure legends

Figure 1. Chemical structures of Uro-A, Uro-B, UroA glucuronide, UroB glucuronide, Uro-C and Uro-D.

Figure 2. Effect of urolithins (100 and 50 μM) on cell proliferation (%) in Caco-2 (**2A**), SW480 (**2B**) and HT-29 (**2C**) cells at 24 and 48 h. Values (%) are expressed as mean \pm SD ($n = 3$). $*p < 0.05$ (two-tailed t test) indicate a significant difference compared to untreated cells.

Figure 3. Analysis of cell cycle distribution (%) of Caco-2 (**3A**), SW480 (**3B**) and HT-29 (**3C**) after treatment with urolithins (100 and 50 μM) at 24 and 48 h. Values (%) are expressed as mean ($n = 3$). $*p \leq 0.05$ indicates a significant difference compared to untreated (control) cells.

Figure 4. Chromatographic profile (305 nm) of cell media in HT-29 cells showing the presence of the metabolites at 0 and 48 h of treatment: (**1**) Uro-A ($m/z^- 227$); (**2**) Uro-A glucuronide ($m/z^- 403$); (**3**) Uro-B ($m/z^- 211$); (**4**) Uro-B glucuronide ($m/z^- 387$); (**5**) Uro-C ($m/z^- 243$); (**6, 7 and 8**) Uro-C glucuronide ($m/z^- 419$) and (**9, 10 and 11**) Uro-C methyl glucuronide ($m/z^- 433$).

Figure 5. (**5A**) Cell metabolism of urolithin aglycones in colon cancer cells. Presence of Uro-A and -B and/or Uro-A and Uro-B glur (%). Data are expressed as mean values ($n = 3$). (**5B**) Effect of different ABC transporter inhibitors plus Uro-A or Uro-B (100 μM) on cell proliferation (%) in HT-29 cells at 24 and 48 h. Values (%) are expressed as mean \pm SD ($n = 3$). $*p < 0.05$ (two-tailed t test) indicates a significant difference compared to untreated cells.

Table 1

Comparative inhibition of cell proliferation (%) in colon cancer cell lines after treatment with Uro-A, Uro-B and their corresponding glucuronides at 24 and 48 h.

Treatments	Caco-2		SW480		HT-29	
	24 h	48 h	24 h	48 h	24 h	48 h
Uro-A (100 μ M)	53.8 \pm 3.1 ^a	72.0 \pm 1.0 ^a	39.2 \pm 4.6 ^a	64.7 \pm 0.9 ^a	49.2 \pm 5.1 ^a	59.1 \pm 2.8 ^a
Uro-A glucuronide (100 μ M)	21.1 \pm 3.1 ^{a,b}	30.8 \pm 3.8 ^{a,b}	5.4 \pm 2.8 ^b	24.7 \pm 3.7 ^{a,b}	9.1 \pm 2.6 ^b	11.4 \pm 3.2 ^{a,b}
Uro-A (50 μ M)	29.1 \pm 6.4 ^a	56.0 \pm 1.1 ^a	31.4 \pm 3.0 ^a	52.5 \pm 1.9 ^a	33.9 \pm 7.5 ^a	27.1 \pm 3.5 ^a
Uro-A glucuronide (50 μ M)	8.2 \pm 3.2 ^b	15.8 \pm 2.3 ^{a,b}	2.3 \pm 1.3 ^b	12.3 \pm 2.3 ^{a,b}	6.9 \pm 2.1 ^b	6.7 \pm 1.7 ^b
Uro-B (100 μ M)	26.7 \pm 3.0 ^a	52.3 \pm 3.1 ^a	16.3 \pm 2.3 ^a	14.3 \pm 4.8 ^a	23.6 \pm 0.6 ^a	35.4 \pm 9.3 ^a
Uro-B glucuronide (100 μ M)	17.3 \pm 5.5 ^{a,b}	27.0 \pm 2.0 ^{a,b}	7.8 \pm 2.0 ^b	9.1 \pm 3.0	2.2 \pm 1.2 ^b	9.5 \pm 1.5 ^{a,b}
Uro-B (50 μ M)	18.2 \pm 1.2 ^a	26.4 \pm 2.0 ^a	1.0 \pm 5.1	4.5 \pm 2.7	17.1 \pm 6.5 ^a	21.5 \pm 2.6 ^a
Uro-B glucuronide (50 μ M)	10.9 \pm 2.7 ^{a,b}	15.9 \pm 2.4 ^{a,b}	5.1 \pm 2.1	7.9 \pm 2.8	1.4 \pm 0.7 ^b	6.7 \pm 1.9 ^b

Values (%) are expressed as mean \pm SD (n = 3). ^aSignificant difference ($p < 0.05$) compared to untreated cells. ^bSignificant difference between aglycone/glucuronide pairs.

Figure 1.

Urolithin A (Uro-A)

Urolithin B (Uro-B)

Urolithin A glucuronide

Urolithin B glucuronide

R1 or R2 = OH and R1 or R2 = Glucuronic acid

Urolithin C (Uro-C)

Urolithin D (Uro-D)

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

Figure 5.

